

Source Unknown: Investigating Spain's Unaccounted Methane Emissions

124 methane plumes detected in Spain by IMEO-UNEP
75 have no identified source (orphan plumes)

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Case #1: Plume ID 8e0591cb-32af-4ade-9d59-1cdb14f9def0
Detection: 2025-12-16 | Tile: 2025-10-04
Lat: 41.77 Long: 0.53 | Almenar, Lleida, Spain
Satellite: Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI - ESA
Detection/Quantification: CAMS/ECMWF/SRON
Flux rate: 67000.0 | std: 24000.0
Wind_u: 4.38 | Wind_v: -0.38 | Speed: 4.39
Source: None attributed

Three candidate sources are identified within the plume's proximity:

(1) Water reservoir WR1, constructed between ~2019 and 2022 over a former clay extraction site, located 300 m from the detection centroid. Prior to construction, the site was subject to approximately 10 years of extractive activity (2009–2019), as documented in the aerial image sequence on page 3.

(2) A cluster of clay quarries and associated landfill mounds operated by a local ceramics manufacturer, located 750 m to 1.9 km from the detection point, covering a total of 62.6 ha of mining activity recorded between 1996 and the present.

(3) Fifteen PRTR-registered livestock facilities (predominantly swine) within a 5 km radius.

Site	Parcel	Activity starts	Activity ends	Area (m ²)
LF1	38	1996 (1)	Active	17.270
	54	1996 (1)	Active	27.886
	40	2002	Active	12.173
RQ1	68N	2002 (1) (2)	2010	22.000
	53	2002 (1) (2)	2007 (1)	15.000
RQ2	64	2007	2010	8.733
	68S	2002 (1) (2)	2010	31.154
	66	2007	2010	9.651
RQ3	67	2007	2010	23.542
	70	2002 (1) (2)	2005	30.960
	83	2002 (2)	2005	27.432
LF2	65	2008	Active	13.310
	69	2005 (2)	2010 (1) Active	15.626
	74	2007	Active	15.642
	81	2007 (1) 2009	Active	47.266
	195	2007 (1) 2009	Active	23.076
	194	2007 (1) 2009	Active	33.396
RQ4	82	2008 (1)	Active	12.100
	84	2008 (1)	Active	20.000
	85	2009	Active	15.375
RQ4	113	2002 (2)	2005	54.606
RQ5	133	1996 (2)	2002 (2)	24.244
	135	2002 (2)	2007 (2)	90.000
LF3	100	1996 (2)	2011	15.563
RQ6	112	1996 (2)	2002 (2)	20.199
(1) Partial use of the parcel				Total
(2) Possibly before (missing previous year/s)				62,6 ha

- Methane plume & wind direction
- PRTR-registered facilities (mostly swine farming) declaring methane emissions within a 5km radius.
- Landfill (LF)
- Restored Quarry (RQ)
- Water Reservoir (WR)

Water Reservoir WR1

Aerial image analysis of WR1 (2008–2024) reveals two distinct phases. Between 2009 and 2019, the site exhibits progressive excavation consistent with clay extraction, including exposed subsoil, irregular terrain modification, and absence of impermeable lining works. From 2020 onward, construction of the reservoir structure becomes visible, with completion and water impoundment occurring by 2022.

The infrared sequence shows no persistent anomalous vegetation signal prior to flooding that would indicate large-scale organic material burial; however, the extended pre-construction phase and the confirmed extractive activity raise the question of what backfill materials — if any — were deposited in the excavated volume before lining works began.

The construction timeline of reservoir WR2 (8.7 ha, comparable in scale to WR1) confirms that a facility of this type can be completed within 3 years. This establishes that the sustained earthworks visible at the WR1 site between 2009 and 2019 — a period spanning approximately 10 years — are inconsistent with reservoir construction and are instead consistent with prolonged extractive activity.

WR1 Project Description by Voltes Group

According to the project description published by contractor Voltes Group, approximately 350,000 m³ of "unsuitable soils" were sent to an external landfill. The composition and destination of these materials, and whether any organic-rich fill was introduced into the site before impoundment, remains unverified.

Modernization project for the irrigation system of the Bassanova Irrigation Community – Almenar

July 10, 2022 by admin

Construction of a regulatory reservoir and installation of flow control elements at the pumping station. This project involves the construction of a regulatory irrigation reservoir in the municipality of Almenar (Lleida), covering an area of 12 hectares and with an approximate capacity of 1,000,000 m³. The reservoir will be connected to the Community's existing pumping station and reservoir to increase water reserves and improve irrigation management.

The reservoir is mostly excavated below the natural ground level, with an approximate earth movement of 900,000 m³, of which around 350,000 m³ are unsuitable soils sent to a landfill, about 300,000 m³ are gravels that are reused off-site, and 250,000 m³ correspond to clays used to provide the necessary impermeability to the reservoir walls. The interior slopes will be lined with riprap boulders for wave protection. The reservoir will have a maximum height of 13 m and a perimeter of 1,500 m. Completion is scheduled for October 2021.

Source: <https://www.voltes.com/es/proyecto-de-modernizacion-del-riego-de-la-comunidad-de-regantes-de-la-bassanova-almenar/>

LF2 site

LF2 is the most active and largest of the identified landfill-category sites, with documented activity beginning in 2007 across multiple cadastral parcels and remaining active through 2025. The aerial time series shows a progressive accumulation of elevated material deposits, particularly concentrated in parcel 82-84 (see next page).

Infrared imagery does not show the persistent high-biomass signature that would be expected from recently deposited sewage sludge or organic industrial waste; dominant tones are consistent with bare mineral substrate. However, infrared reflectance alone cannot rule out subsurface organic burial beneath a mineral cap layer — a documented practice in mine restoration. The site operator was contacted directly prior to publication and verbally confirmed exclusive use of inert backfill materials, but has not yet provided the regulatory documentation — approved restoration plan and waste acceptance records issued by the Generalitat de Catalunya — that would substantiate this claim and allow this site to be formally excluded as a methane source.

Large spoil mound at LF2— estimated at approximately 140m in width at its base and 20m high from 2010 Google Street View. **The nature of this material (inert extractive waste vs. organic-rich fill) is the central unresolved question.**

Dimensions estimated from Google Street View and Google Earth. Values are approximate ($\pm 20\%$) and provided for scale reference only.

Local Methane Reported Emissions vs. Satellite-Measured Flux

For visualization purposes, individual facility emissions and their combined total (blue bars) are magnified by 100x in the chart. Values in the accompanying table represent actual calculated hourly averages based on 2024 PRTR official reports, the most recent dataset available at the time of this analysis. This ensures the most accurate comparison between reported industrial activity and the satellite detection event of December 2025

Conclusion

The satellite detection of a $67,000 \pm 24,000$ kg/h methane flux over the Almenar area (Lleida) on December 16, 2025 represents the largest orphan plume detected in Spain by ESA's Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI instrument to date. No registered emission source in the area accounts for more than a negligible fraction of this flux: the combined PRTR-reported emissions of all 15 facilities within a 5 km radius total 53.73 kg/h, a factor of 1,247 below the detected value.

Of the three candidate sources investigated, livestock farming is effectively ruled out on quantitative grounds. The two remaining suspects — water reservoir WR1 and the LF2 landfill complex — both involve significant earthworks over clay extraction sites in an area where mine restoration using organic-rich materials (sewage sludge, industrial biosolids) is not only a documented industry practice but an officially regulated and actively promoted one. (1)

Wind direction at the time of detection (west-to-east) is geometrically inconsistent with LF2 as the sole source, but does not exclude WR1, located 300 m upwind of the detection centroid. Wind conditions at the moment of a single satellite overpass are not representative of persistent emission patterns and should not be used as a definitive attribution criterion.

Next Steps

The priority action is to obtain the official mine restoration plans for both WR1 and all clay quarry parcels (listed on page 2) from the Generalitat de Catalunya (Direcció General Canvi Climàtic i Qualitat Ambiental), including waste acceptance records and material characterization data. If organic fill was approved and deposited, anaerobic decomposition in a sealed subsurface environment is a plausible mechanism for methane generation at this scale.

Simultaneously, a formal data request to IMEO-UNEP or Copernicus-ESA for any additional detection events over the same coordinates in prior periods, as well as field measurements by the relevant local authorities, would establish whether this is an isolated event or a persistent source — a distinction critical for source attribution and resolution of the largest unattributed methane emission event recorded in Spain.

(1) RESTOFANGS programme (1992–present): technical and administrative protocol for the use of urban sewage sludge as organic amendment in quarry restoration, funded by the Catalan Water Agency (ACA) and the Catalan Waste Agency, developed by CREAM/UAB. <https://www.creaf.cat/es/restauracion-de-actividades-extractivas-con-lodos-de-depuradora>